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Design of an efficient klystron

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ABSTRACT

Several future high energy accelerator projects implying large demands for RF power in the range of 10 to 100 MW (FCC-ee, ILC, CLIC, CompactLight, etc) will benefit from increasing the efficiency of the power sources. In this deliverable, we report about a design study of a 12 GHz and around 20 MW peak power klystron with improved efficiency by more than 10% with respect to the tubes available commercially, which could be a candi-date for use at the future CompactLight FEL.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

This document summarizes the work done in ARIES within the frame of deliverable 4.2 at CEA. It consists of a design study of a klystron in the X-band, intending to improve the efficiency of existing klystrons by at least 10%, and thus lower significantly the electrical consumption of RF power sources needed for future accelerator projects.

In the introduction, we mention the need for improved RF power sources in the realm of new accelerator projects needing in the range of 10 to 100 MW RF power, and then describe in part 2 the specifications of the klystron chosen for this design study, that is a 20 MW peak power klystron operating at 12 GHz, which could be used in future CompactLight FELs.

In part 3, we describe the most relevant methods to improve klystron efficiency, most based on new techniques of bunching optimization in the interaction line. In part 4, we summarize the simulation tools used for designing a klystron. In part 5, we present a summary of the results obtained in the frame of EuCARD-2 for a prototype "kladistron" operating at 5 GHz, using an adiabatic bunching, and the lessons learned from it that we take into account in this ARIES new design study.

Part 6 represents the core of this deliverable, where the design studies performed for this 12 GHz klystron are presented and discussed in detail. The crucial part of this study to improve the overall efficiency of the klystron is to optimize the interaction line and the multi-cell output cavity using electromagnetic field simulations. An overview of different beam focusing solutions is also proposed.

Defining the RF efficiency as the ratio between the extracted to input beam power, using different approaches we obtain a klystron design with an efficiency of about 65%, well above the RF efficiency of existing klystrons in the X-band which are about 50% efficient.

1 Introduction

With the emergence of new accelerator projects always more demanding concerning the amount of energy drawn from the power outlet by their Radio Frequency systems, improving energy-efficient conversion of electrical grid power into RF is becoming a key aspect in the approval process for these new facilities and ensure sustainability over the long term. This is particularly true for electrons colliders like FCC, ILC, or CLIC, which will need RF systems delivering average power of 100 MW or above [1]. Another example with large RF power consumption is CompactLight, a prototype for a new compact FEL. Efforts have been engaged recently to stretch the efficiency of existing RF power sources to higher levels, in particular for klystrons where modern bunching techniques help to improve the collection of extracted RF power.

The present study, focused on an efficient klystron design in the X-band, is in line with these efforts and is in part a continuation of a previous project in the framework of the EuCARD-2 program. After having introduced the detailed specifications for the studied klystron and presented the different methods and tools to improve its efficiency, the full optimization process of the interaction line and the output cavity will be presented. This study mostly concentrates on this last aspect, as it is the key to obtain higher efficiencies than achieved by existing on the shelf klystrons in the X-band which are around 50% (e.g. the E37116 12 GHz klystron from CANON [2]). Although not designed in this study, we discuss ways to obtain a beam focusing system drawing much less current than normal conducting solenoid, essential for low duty cycle applications.

2 Specifications for the design study

New compact accelerators operating in the X-band such as CLIC (Compact Linear Collider) or Compact Light will require high power (10 MW to 70 MW) and high frequency (11.994 GHz) RF sources. SLAC has already developed 50 MW to 70 MW RF sources operating in the X-band [3] and efforts are ongoing to increase the efficiency of these RF sources [4]. For this project, a klystron operating in the X-band with an extracted power of about 20 MW will be studied. Maximum efficiency achievable by a klystron is highly correlated with its perveance, defined as:

$$K = \frac{I_{cathode}}{V_{cathode}^{1.5}} \quad (1)$$

The lower the perveance, the easiest it is to achieve high efficiency. Nevertheless, decreasing the perveance will increase the gap voltage, especially for the last cavities, and could lead to RF-breakdown. After preliminary studies, a perveance of $1.0 \mu A/V^{3/2}$ seems to be a good compromise to achieve high efficiency, keeping the gap voltage of the last cavities low.

At the perveance of $1.0 \mu A/V^{3/2}$, we can aim for an RF efficiency approaching 70%, which would be a considerable improvement over the existing klystrons (see Figure 1). With such an efficiency, the output power of 20 MW would be achieved with the DC beam power of only 28.8 MW. This beam power together with the assumed micro-perveance set the cathode voltage to 240 kV and the beam current to 120 A, which we therefore use as our design parameters.

The duty cycle of the accelerator projects for which such a klystron can be used is very low, less than 1% – see Table 1 [5], [6]. For the required pulse parameters, it is reasonable to assume the surface electric field of 100 MV/m as a breakdown limit (based on the experience gained in the on-going XBOX experiment at CERN [7]). Therefore, this value has been considered as a limitation for our design study.

	Repetition rate [Hz]	Pulse length [μs]	Duty cycle [%]
Compact Light 1	100.0	1.500	0.01500
Compact Light 2	250.0	0.150	0.00375
Compact Light 3	1000.0	1.500	0.15000
CLIC K244	50.0	0.244	0.00122

Table 1: Pulse parameters.

High efficient klystrons are more vulnerable to instability and spurious oscillations. In microwave tubes, the small-signal regime corresponds to a linear relation between input and output powers. The lower the small-signal gain, the more robust will be the klystron, regarding the oscillations. Moreover, small-signal and large-signal gain are highly correlated.

Figure 1: Empirical fit between efficiency and perveance (in $\mu A/V^{3/2}$) as presented in [8]. Klystron wavelengths are represented in cm.

Increasing the injected RF-power in the first cavity input coupler will necessarily decrease the large-signal gain and so the optimized small-signal gain. On the other hand, high power amplifiers will be required. Limiting the large-signal gain to 50dB has been finally chosen as a good compromise. It would imply that to achieve 20 MW output, the injected signal in the input cavity should be about 53 dBm, allowing the use of regular amplifiers.

3 Different methods of improving klystron efficiency

3.1 Decreasing the perveance, MBK approach

Maximum efficiency achievable by a klystron is highly correlated with its perveance. Low perveance means weak space charge forces, which translates to better bunching and easier power extraction in the output cavity. This fact is clearly shown by the empirical fit of the klystron efficiency as a function of the perveance, introduced in [8] and depicted in Figure 1.

A straightforward way to decrease the perveance (while keeping the same beam power) is to increase the DC cathode voltage. However, increasing the voltage beyond the chosen value of 240 kV faces technological difficulties in the modulator design. It also requires a longer output cavity with a large number of cells in order to avoid RF breakdown, meaning a more complex design with more parasitic modes.

There are ways to decrease the effective perveance experienced by the beam's particles without increasing the cathode voltage. One way is to use a Multiple Beam Klystron (MBK) – a well-known solution to increase the efficiency [9, 10]. A similar approach is to use a hollow (or sheet) beam with the particles concentrated on a ring (or line) and therefore exerting lower space charge forces on other particles [11]. However, all of these solutions are technologically difficult to realize for a klystron that is both high power and high frequency (i.e. requiring a compact beam). For an MBK, one way to circumvent this problem is to spread out the multiple beams by using an HOM MBK rather than the usual fundamental mode MBK. Unfortunately, efforts to design a high frequency HOM MBK resulted in only a modest efficiency due to the intrinsically low impedance of the HOM cavities [12].

For these reasons, we decided not to use any of the described methods, opting for a single beam design with a moderate perveance of $1 \mu A/V^{3/2}$. Instead, efforts have been focused on exploring novel bunching circuit configurations (see below), which allow increasing the efficiency without decreasing the perveance.

3.2 Core Oscillation Method (COM)

The Core Oscillation Method introduced in [13] consists of using a cavity highly coupled with the beam, to congregate the peripheral electrons of the bunch, while the electrons in the core of the bunch are “oscillating” through the tube as illustrated in Figure 2:

Figure 2: Schematic Phase diagram of the bunch through the tube, left traditional bunching, right COM bunching

After the bunching cavity, all the electrons will receive a kick toward the bunch center. If the drift tube is long enough, the electrons in the bunch core will be repulsed resulting in a core oscillation, while the peripheral electron, affected by weaker space charges, will continue to drift toward the bunch center. After the core oscillation, the space charge within the bunch may be well homogenous, as well as the electron speed. After multiple core oscillations, the bunch should be better congregated than the one with a conventional bunching technique and the power extracted in the last cavity should be maximum. This method has been applied recently to increase klystron efficiency. Nevertheless, it implies longer tubes, which may be a problem for tubes operating at low frequency. However, in the X-band, compactness of the klystron is not an issue and this method has been retained amongst others to optimize the bunching circuit for this study.

3.3 Using harmonic cavity (Bunch Align Collect – BAC and Core Stabilization bunching Method – CSM)

To solve the problem of compactness for low-frequency klystron, BAC [14] and CSM [15] methods have been developed. The strategy for these methods consists of dividing the bunch, to reduce the space charge effect and then rebuild it. To divide the bunch, a harmonic cavity is used as illustrated in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Schematic Phase diagram of the bunch through the tube, left traditional bunching, right BAC or CSM bunching

Like in the COM, the bunch core oscillates, while peripheral electrons are continuously moving to the bunch center. Klystron based on these methods may achieve the same efficiency as the ones using the COM, but they may be shorter. A drawback of these methods is the oscillation of the harmonic frequency. If this method were used on a 12 GHz klystron, one of its cavities should oscillate at least at 24 GHz. To avoid the propagation of the fundamental mode through the tube at this frequency and so the coupling between the cavities, the tube radius would have to be smaller than 3.75 mm. Since the compactness in the X-band is not an issue and we should avoid the wave propagation through the tube, these methods have not been considered for this study.

3.4 Adiabatic bunching

The adiabatic method introduced in [16] and applied in [17] consists of using low coupling cavity close to each other, to congregate peripheral electrons of the bunch progressively as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Schematic Phase diagram of the bunch through the tube, left traditional bunching, right adiabatic bunching

The smooth progression of the bunch formation may avoid strong variations of the entropy, unlike the COM or BAC method. It has to be noticed that multi-cavity klystron may be more vulnerable to spurious oscillations. Therefore, using this method implies being vigilant regarding this problem. Similarly to the COM, using this method may increase the tube length, but as mentioned for the COM, for tubes operating in the X band, this is not an issue. Therefore, this method has been retained amongst others to optimize the bunching circuit for this study.

4 Simulations tools

During this project, different simulation tools have been used. A detailed study comparing them has been previously conducted [18]. Below we briefly explain the key differences between them. These simulation tools are mainly based on two different methods:

- Disk Model: AJDISK [19] and Klyc [20];
- Particle in Cell (PIC): MAGIC 2D [21] and CST [22].

With the Disk Model method, the electron beam is modeled as a cylinder divided into multiple disks. These disks are eventually divided into multiple layers to get a better precision as illustrated in Figure 5. Nevertheless, this may increase the simulation time.

Figure 5: bunching process with Disk Model method. Top, 1D 1 layer, bottom 2D multiple layers

An iterative algorithm calculates the longitudinal modulation of the beam through the tube and so the phase of each disk regarding the bunch core. For each cavity, the electric field interacting with the beam may be calculated regarding some characteristic parameter of the cavity or using an eigensolver to take the real geometry of the cavity into account. This method provides approximated but fast results. Only steady-state performances can be estimated with this method.

The Disk Model method is well suited to test multiple klystron configurations during an optimization. Nevertheless, the estimated performances need to be finalized and validated via PIC solvers, such as MAGIC2D or CST. These tools may also provide the transient state performances of the klystron. With the PIC method, the beam is modeled using charged particles, interacting with a permanent magnetic field and electromagnetic field induced in the cavities. The calculation time is significantly increased, about a few hours to few days, but the result is much more reliable.

5 Feedback from EuCARD-2 kladistron results

All the work described in this section was performed under the framework of EuCARD-2 (2013-2017), where we studied high efficiency - high frequency klystrons in close collaboration between CEA Saclay and Thales Electron Devices.

The first aim of this study was to consider a high-power 12 GHz klystron to be used in CLIC. A new electron beam bunching technique has been proposed to increase the beam-to-RF interaction efficiency above the state-of-the-art limits ($> 65\%$) [16]. This method is inspired by the Radio Frequency Quadrupole (RFQ) based injectors which bunch adiabatically a CW (continuous mode) hadron beam with more than 95% transmission. The newly proposed device, called kladistron, includes a large number of cavities (typically 15 to 20, which is twice as many as in a conventional klystron) separated by short drift tubes. This enables giving a “soft kick” to the beam in a large number of cavities instead of a “large kick” to the beam in a small number of cavities (see 3.4).

Figure 6: Principle of adaptation of the TH2166 to the kladistron. The elements in blue are kept from the TH2166 while the elements in orange (the intermediate cavities) are re-designed for the kladistron.

5.1 Fabrication and test of a 5 GHz kladistron prototype

As a first experimental validation of the kladistron principle, we decided to transform an existing klystron and only change the interaction line. The chosen tube is the 4.9 GHz – 50 kW CW TH2166 klystron developed by Thales, which has an efficiency of 50%. This tube is made with 6 cavities while the adapted kladistron is designed with 16 cavities [23].

Figure 6 shows the reused TH2166 elements: the gun, the solenoid, the collector, as well as the input and output cavities. The modified elements are the 14 intermediate cavities replacing the existing 4 cavities. This is a conservative approach since it allows to focus only on the interaction line. However, this approach brings some constraints: the length of the interaction line is limited and the magnetic field profile cannot be modified.

The design of the intermediate cavities was realized using 1D-code AJDisk [19], 2D-code Klys2D [24] and 2D-PIC code Magic [21]. This design predicted an efficiency of 60 %, ten points higher than for the TH2166. The cavities are made of copper, and their quality factor was lowered from ≈ 3000 to ≈ 1400 by deposition of titanium on one of the cavity faces. Moreover, the presence of titanium helps to reduce multipacting. The cavity parts are then brazed together (Figure 2, center) and the whole kladistron, with gun and collector, is assembled (Figure 2, right). Taking the complexity of the manufacturing into account, we considered that an increase of the efficiency from 50 % to 55 % would be significant to consist into a first validation of the kladistron principle.

Figure 7: Left: Brazed interaction line. Right: assembled kladistron

The kladistron was tested in Thales facilities on the test bench dedicated to the TH2166. The output power and efficiency were determined from RF measurements and confirmed with calorimetric measurements. Finally, it appeared that:

- The efficiency reached a maximum of 40.8 %, lower than expected and even lower than the standard TH2166 efficiency
- We observed the existence of an unexpected spurious oscillation, also present in pure diode mode, without input signal.

From retro-simulations and post-mortem analysis emerged some issues which must be anticipated for such high-efficiency klystrons.

5.2 Lessons learned and potential improvements

After RF measurements, the kladistron was disassembled and the frequencies, loss, and external Q factors were measured. Some differences were observed compared to the design values. The reason is that, first, the frequencies could not be adjusted after cavities brazing, due to deflection of the tuning systems, and second, the interaction line was probably slightly deformed during the manufacturing process. Since the kladistron performances are very sensitive to the cavities frequencies, it results that these small frequency shifts are responsible for the loss of efficiency.

Moreover, the small-signal gain was measured during the tests, and compared to AJDisk calculations for two sets of frequencies: the design frequencies and the post-mortem measured frequencies. Both measured and post-mortem calculated gain reach much higher values than expected from the design frequencies, especially around the spurious oscillation frequency. This is probably the cause of the spurious oscillation. We suspect that the back-streaming electrons reflected by the collector up to the input cavity form a feedback loop on the gain. The high gain value at 4.96 GHz could then be responsible for an auto-induced oscillation.

This experience shows that it is crucial to assure accurate frequency in operation to such klystrons and this is detailed hereafter.

5.2.1 Cavity tuning

The solution adopted for this kladistron was based on the deformation of a thick membrane between the inside and the outside of each cavity by the movement of brazed pins, which were aimed to translate along drillings (which can be observed in Figure 7 left) [25]. The tuning operation was performed through plastic deformation of those membranes. The cavity frequencies should be adjusted once, after the complete brazing of the interaction line, when the cavity frequencies can still be measured with antennas. Despite promising results on cavities prototypes, the brazing between pins (cupronickel) and cavity membrane (copper) finally broke. The two last cavities, whose influence on the klystron efficiency is maximal (see Figure 8), could still be tuned by mechanical deformation of the irises with an external tool.

Figure 8: Effect on each cavity detuning on the efficiency for the kladistron. The deviation from specified efficiency is given in percentage. The detuning values, from -10 MHz to +10 MHz are indicated, by shades of blue [17].

Moreover, the comparison between the frequencies at this stage and after klystron disassembly shows that the frequencies had shifted, probably during the final kladistron assembly. Consequently, a solution must be developed to guarantee frequency accuracy after this final assembly. One solution could be the implementation of in-situ tuning systems, able to adjust frequency during klystron operation. Such solutions have already been studied for other klystrons [26] and could be implemented in future studies. Another solution, especially appropriate for large-scale production, is to guarantee cavities frequency by a well-controlled fabrication process. This process has been widely developed for the X-band manufacturing at CERN [27].

5.2.2 Small signal gain limitation

Klystrons with a large number of cavities tend to present high gain, with a higher risk of oscillations. It is then essential to limit the small-signal gain during the interaction line design process. We took this parameter into consideration in the design process of the 12 GHz klystron presented in this report (see 6.2.1).

5.2.3 Reflected electrons and collector design

The kladistron was assembled with the collector designed for the standard TH2166 klystron. This collector played correctly its main role and dissipated the energy of the electrons without damage. However, the number of reflected electrons was apparently high enough to generate an oscillation loop in the kladistron. This phenomenon didn't occur for the TH2166 because of its lower gain, and thus any effort for a new design must focus on reducing as much as possible the small-signal gain. However, changing the design of the collector could also help to avoid oscillation loop and instability [28], and the possibility of electron reflection should be considered and simulated in any new design.

6 12 GHz klystron design

Below we describe the high-efficiency 12 GHz klystron designed within the framework of the ARIES project. In 6.1 we discuss the focusing magnet aspects and ways to avoid the losses in a normal conducting solenoid. In 6.2 we describe the process of the RF cavity optimization and present the final RF design. Optimized cavity dimensions are summarized in 6.3. The performance of the designed klystron is analyzed in 6.4. Electron gun and collector designs are not included in this work and can be subjects of future studies.

6.1 Beam focusing

In the klystron simulations presented in this section, the beam is properly focused all along the interaction line. In the frequency-based codes (AJDISK and KlyC) this focusing is intrinsic to the model. In the 2D/3D PIC codes (Magic and CST), a uniform magnetic field is defined in the simulation parameters. Its value derives from the Brillouin flux density which is equal to 0.17 T with our klystron parameters [29]. This value is multiplied by a value between 2 and 3 to obtain the focusing field (See section 7.1.3 of reference [30]), and a standard value is 2.3, which results in $B_{foc} = 0.39$ T. This value is used in all the PIC simulations presented in this chapter, and the results show that this value actually assures a proper beam focusing. The following sections present and discuss the possible focusing schemes.

6.1.1 Normal conducting solenoid

Most of the klystrons use normal conducting solenoids for beam focusing. However, in the case of pulsed klystrons with small duty cycles, the solenoid power supply becomes high compared to the beam power supply. Of course, this situation would be avoided if the solenoid could follow the klystron pulsed mode. However, pulsed magnets are not adapted to high repetition rates.

In the case of our 12 GHz klystron, we have estimated both average beam power and solenoid power supply. The beam pulse power is 28.8 MW and the average power depends on the duty cycle. We have considered four situations: three Compact Light options (1: $0.1kHz/1.5\mu s$), (2: $0.25kHz/0.15\mu s$), (3: $1kHz/1.5\mu s$) [5], and the last CLIC option ($50Hz/0.244\mu s$) [6] (see Table 1). The calculated average beam power is probably underestimated since the real pulse from the modulator is not flat and some power is lost during the rise and fall times. The solenoid power has been estimated by scaling from the TH20610 solenoid (Thales). The results are summarized in Figure 9 and show that in most cases the solenoid supply would require most of the total electrical supply for operating such klystrons.

In conclusion, the use of a normal conducting solenoid would cancel the effort toward high-efficiency klystrons.

Figure 9: Comparison of average beam power/solenoid power for different klystron schemes.

6.1.2 Superconducting solenoid

The power consumption of the focusing solenoid can be drastically reduced by using superconducting technology. Here we only give an order of magnitude which is a scaling of as study made by CERN: the solenoid power is divided by 10 from normal to superconducting (Figure 9) [4]. Then, depending on the considered duty cycle, the solenoid power consumption stays low or in the order of magnitude of the beam power.

We have not developed the study of a superconducting solenoid solution in the frame of ARIES, but it remains an interesting option for future development.

6.1.3 Periodic Permanent Magnet (PPM) focusing

The PPM focusing scheme consists of a periodic series of annular permanent magnets, along the interaction lines, with alternating polarity (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Periodic focusing of an electron beam with permanent magnets [30].

The longitudinal field on axis is close to a sinus and the field direction changes every half period. Since the restoring force is proportional to the square of the field, it is independent of its direction. However, the field pattern is not homogeneous compared to the field from a solenoid, and the beam tends to undulate. If the magnetic period is small enough when compared to the plasma wavelength of the beam then the beam will be focused with sufficient stiffness to maintain the profile.

PPM focusing system is widely used for Traveling Wave Tubes, but more rarely for klystrons. The implementation is more complicated because either the magnets are placed at a distance larger than the cavities radius, and the field is lowered, or they are placed between the cavities, but it is difficult to respect the periodicity.

Moreover, as previously mentioned, the magnet period must be small compared to the plasma wavelength which reduces when the beam voltage is reduced. When a klystron is used in the pulsed mode there is always a point where the magnet period becomes large compared to the plasma wavelength. This is called the "stop band voltage", and during the rise and fall times of the beam pulse, there is an amount of time where the voltage is lower than this value and the beam is not focused anymore. This phenomenon can lead to some deterioration on the inner surface of the klystron.

Finally, one of the drawbacks of permanent magnet focusing is the complexity of the field tuning, contrary to a solenoid where the field can be adjusted to ensure beam focusing.

PPM focusing for klystrons was developed in two accelerator laboratories, SLAC [31] and KEK [32]. They developed Alnico magnets, with encouraging results. The main reason for the discontinuance was the complexity in the field tuning. The magnetic fields generated by the magnets in these laboratories were tuned by partial magnetization and/or demagnetization of the Alnico magnets or attaching magnetic material shims such as iron bars. However, these tuning methods were very complicated, and both laboratories have finally turned

to solenoids [33].

6.1.4 Quasi-Halbach permanent magnet configuration

A permanent magnet configuration different from PPM has been previously proposed and tested for an L-band klystron [33, 34]. It is based on the quasi-Halbach configuration, with the B-field direction remaining constant along the entire interaction line. It requires relatively bulky magnets, however, this does not pose a problem for our compact X-band klystron. Experiments with the beam [33] showed that the RF efficiency of the L-band klystron with the permanent magnet focusing can be slightly lower than that with the solenoid focusing, which was attributed to the multipole magnetic field components. However, the gain due to the absence of the solenoid losses should outweigh this loss in efficiency for low duty cycle machines such as the Compact Light.

A version of the setup from [33, 34], scaled down to fit the ARIES klystron, has been simulated in CST - see Figure 11. The magnet system is split into two retractable sides to allow for the klystron installation. The iron yoke is used to confine the magnetic flux lines, and the iron shields are used to lower the fields in the cathode and the collector regions. Since no detailed designs for the cathode and the collector exist yet, the dimensions of the shields are scaled from the L-band klystron to get a rough idea of the field profile. It should be noted that the ferrite magnets used in the study [33, 34] are not strong enough to provide the required ARIES focusing field of 0.39 Tesla. Nevertheless, preliminary studies showed that it can be achieved with commercially available rare-earth type magnets with the remnant flux of 1.27 Tesla. The higher cost of such magnets is not an issue due to the compactness of the X-band klystron, however, one possible problem is that they tend to be brittle. This fact, together with forces produced by the magnets, might require a support system and additional assembly tools.

Figure 11: Magnetic field profile in the quasi-Halbach configuration. A klystron would fit in the middle of the picture, oriented vertically with the cathode at the top and the collector at the bottom of the picture.

6.1.5 Conclusion on beam focusing

As mentioned in the beginning of this chapter, all the PIC simulations of the present study include a uniform magnetic field equal to 0.39 T without any mention of the focusing method.

This section presents different standard methods for beam focusing in klystrons and disqualifies some of them which are not adapted to our purpose (normal conducting solenoid). For the other ones, some design elements are given, and an overview of the state of the art is presented. However, this is very preliminary and a more in-depth study would be necessary to prove the feasibility and the superiority of one specific focusing scheme.

6.2 RF design

The klystron efficiency optimization is a multivariate parameters problem. To reduce the complexity of this problem, it has been divided into 2 sub-problems:

- The bunching circuit optimization
- The multicell output cavity geometry optimization

6.2.1 Bunching circuit optimization

In 6.2.1.1, a large set of configurations is explored, using a fast but low accuracy simulation tool (AJDISK). In 6.2.1.2, a smaller set of configurations, close to the optimal configuration found in 6.2.1.1, is explored using a slow but more accurate simulation tool (Klyc with four-layer disk model).

6.2.1.1 Optimization based on a genetic algorithm and single-layer disk model simulations

For this type of problem, the optimization cannot be considered as a linear problem and it seems that a stochastic method is well adapted [35]. Therefore, it has been optimized with the Genetic Optimization System Engineering Tool (GOSET), freely available on matlab [36]. A klystron can be fully defined by 6 parameters for each cavity:

- 5 RF parameters: the ratio R/Q , the transit time factor M ; the coupling factor with waveguides Q_{ext} ; the quality factor Q_0 and the resonant frequency f .
- 1 geometrical parameter: the cavity position z .

As presented in [35] or in [37], to reduce the number of variables, only the positions (z_2, \dots, z_n) of the second to the last cavity and the resonant frequency (f_1, \dots, f_{n-1}) of the first to the penultimate cavity are tunable. These parameters will be referred as the vector (x_1, \dots, x_N) . The other RF parameters $(R/Q; M; Q_{ext}; Q_0)$ are fixed and correspond to a pillbox cavity with a 2.2 mm gap length for intermediate cavities and 5 mm gap length for the first cavity. In this part, only the bunching circuit is optimized, therefore, the RF parameters of the last cavity have to be fixed in order to compare the different configurations. The transit time factor for this cavity, which is highly correlated to the efficiency, is especially fixed at 0.8.

To avoid coupling effects and allow the core oscillation, the range distance between two consecutive cavities is [20 mm; 120 mm]. The range of the resonant frequency for the intermediate cavities is [11.5 GHz; 13 GHz], allowing debunching cavities and very low coupling cavities like those used for the adiabatic method. Each configuration is tested using AJDISK (single-layer disk model simulation). Since the performances may depend on simulation parameters such as the number of disks and the number of time steps, three simulations are performed and the one with the lowest efficiency is selected. From the estimated efficiency η and maximum of small-signal gain G_S , a cost function $Cost$, which has to be maximized, is calculated and provided to the GOSET:

$$Cost(x_1, \dots, x_N) = \eta(x_1, \dots, x_N) + \frac{10}{G_S(x_1, \dots, x_N)} \quad (2)$$

This cost function is empiric and takes into account the trade-off between the gain in large-signal (correlated with high efficiency) and the gain in small-signal that may generate spurious oscillations. For instance, a klystron with 70% efficiency and a maximum of small-signal gain $G_S = 60 \text{ dB}$ has almost the same cost function as a klystron with 69% efficiency and a maximum of small-signal gain $G_S = 57 \text{ dB}$. This means that the algorithm may accept to lose 1% efficiency if the small-signal gain is reduced by 3 dB.

Different optimizations have been performed, for different tube radii (3 mm or 4 mm). Large tube radii may be favorable to higher efficiency. On the other hand, the cavity should not be coupled and the tube radius should be small enough to attenuate the fundamental mode TE11. Therefore the tube radius has been set to 4 mm.

The beam radius has been set to 2.4 mm, corresponding to a fill factor of about 60%. It is large enough to get the highest efficiency but small enough to take into account its expansion in the last cavity.

The optimization has also been performed for different numbers of cavities. The optimized cost function for these optimizations is depicted on Figure 12.

Figure 12: Optimised cost function vs. number of cavities.

From 5 to 7 cavities, the more cavities there are, the better will be the optimized cost function. For 7 to 9 cavities, the optimized cost function may be the same. Increasing the number of cavities will increase the number of variables and also the difficulty for the

stochastic algorithm to converge on the best configuration. This explains the lower cost function achieved for the 9 and 10 cavities klystron optimizations compared to 8 cavities klystron optimization. Finally, the optimization has been performed with 8 cavities.

The parameters for the best configuration obtained via this optimization process are presented in Table 2.

Cavity ID	R/Q	M	Q_{ext}	Q_0	f (GHz)	z (mm)
1	90	0.5800	270	5600	11.988	0.00
2	40	0.6660	95000	2800	11.990	64.70
3	40	0.6660	95000	2800	12.554	107.00
4	40	0.6660	95000	2800	12.587	143.40
5	40	0.6660	95000	2800	12.168	181.70
6	40	0.6660	95000	2800	12.286	217.20
7	40	0.6660	95000	2800	12.113	262.40
8	40	0.8000	80	6000	11.994	287.40

Table 2: AJDISK parameters of the optimized 8 cavities klystron

The beam current modulation calculated by AJDISK is depicted in Figure 13 and the Applegate diagram calculated by Klyc is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 13: Beam current modulation along the tube for the optimized bunching circuit, calculated by AJDISK. I_n is the amplitude of the modulated current for the harmonic n and $I_0 = 120 A$ is the amplitude of the injected beam current. The center of the first cavity is at $z = 0 m$.

Figure 14: Applegate diagram for the optimized bunching circuit, calculated by Klyc. Each line represents the progression of the phase of a disk within the bunch along the tube.

The optimized configuration is an hybridization of the COM and the adiabatic method. Between the second and the fifth cavity, the core is oscillating. This oscillation is extended with the third and fourth low coupling cavity, corresponding to the adiabatic method. The same strategy can be observed between the fifth and the seventh cavity.

The small-signal gain, calculated on AJDISK is presented in Figure 15. It is smaller than 56 dB . Then, this bunching circuit should be stable and spurious oscillations should be avoided.

Figure 15: Small-signal gain, calculated by AJDISK.

6.2.1.2 Refinement based on multi-layer disk model simulations

Single-layer disk model simulations performed on AJDISK provided faster but less accurate results than multi-layer disk model or PIC simulations. It was well suited to test multiple configurations during the stochastic optimisation. For a better accuracy, the resulting bunching circuit has been simulated in Klyc using a four-layer disk model and the axial electric field calculated via the eigenmode solver. The last cavity has been replaced by a generic double gap cavity. The calculated efficiency was η_0 . The resulting beam current modulation along the tube for each layer is presented on Figure 16.

Figure 16: Beam current modulation along the tube, calculated by Klyc with four-layer disks for the initial optimized bunching circuit. $Jz1$ is the amplitude of the modulated current for each layer of radius r and $Jz0$ is the amplitude of the injected beam current.

It is clear that this beam current modulation for the layers with the smallest radii could be improved to increase the tube efficiency. A new set of $M=30$ new configurations has been generated randomly, changing the $N=14$ parameters (x_{01}, \dots, x_{0N}) by small variations $(\partial x_{k1}, \dots, \partial x_{kN})$ for the new configuration k . Simulated on Klyc with four-layer disks, the calculated efficiency η_k is approximated with a Taylor series:

$$\eta_k = \eta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x_i} \partial x_{ki} \quad (3)$$

Where the coefficients of the Taylor series $\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x_i}$ are unknown. For the M configurations, the calculated efficiencies are:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \eta_1 \\ \vdots \\ \eta_M \end{pmatrix} = \eta_0 + \begin{pmatrix} \partial x_{11} & \cdots & \partial x_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \partial x_{M1} & \cdots & \partial x_{MN} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x_1} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x_N} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The vector of the unknown coefficients of the Taylor serie is:

$$\Delta \mathbf{E} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x_1} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x_N} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The Jacobian matrix is:

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{pmatrix} \partial x_{11} & \cdots & \partial x_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \partial x_{M1} & \cdots & \partial x_{MN} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

If we note \mathbf{E} the efficiency variation:

$$\mathbf{E} = \begin{pmatrix} \eta_1 \\ \vdots \\ \eta_M \end{pmatrix} - \eta_0 = \mathbf{J} \Delta \mathbf{E} \quad (7)$$

The vector $\Delta \mathbf{E}$ is estimated via the least square method as:

$$\Delta \mathbf{E} = (\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{J})^{-1} \mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{E} \quad (8)$$

A new configuration is finally found changing the paramaters (x_{01}, \dots, x_{0N}) by the small variation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \partial x_1 \\ \vdots \\ \partial x_N \end{pmatrix} = 0.01 * \Delta \mathbf{E} \quad (9)$$

This new configuration provides a new efficiency, increased by 1%. This process can be repeated until it converges to the highest efficiency. The final configuration is presented in Table 3. The cavity frequencies remains about the same but the drift tube lengths between the cavities are slightly modified to take the radial dependencies of the beam modulation into account for the COM and adiabatic methods. This beam current modulation is presented in Figure 17 and is well improved for disk layers with the smallest radii.

Cavity ID	gap (mm)	Q_{ext}	f (GHz)	z (mm)
1	5.0	270	11.986	0.00
2	2.2	95000	12.000	65.50
3	2.2	95000	12.552	106.70
4	2.2	95000	12.577	144.50
5	2.2	95000	12.176	180.90
6	2.2	95000	12.236	217.50
7	2.2	95000	12.105	261.10
8	NA	114	11.994	284.30

Table 3: Final parameters of the 8 cavities klystron optimized with Klyc, using four-layer disk.

Figure 17: Beam current modulation along the tube, calculated by Klyc with four-layer disks for the final optimized bunching circuit. $Jz1$ is the amplitude of the modulated current for each layer of radius r and $Jz0$ is the amplitude of the injected beam current.

6.2.2 Output cavity optimization

In the early studies, the output cavity has been optimized independently from the bunching circuit, as was presented in [38]. However, in what is described below, the bunched beam at the end of the penultimate cavity was used as an input for the output cavity optimization.

Optimizations of a 2-cell output cavity and a 3-cell output cavity were performed. The 3-cell design had the potential advantage of the reduced surface fields and the increased ef-

efficiency thanks to the longer interaction region. After the optimization, the best-performing 3-cell cavity did have slightly lower surface fields, however, it showed practically no advantage over the 2-cell cavity in terms of efficiency. More than that, the last cell of the 3-cell design was weakly coupled to the first two, and almost all of the output power was extracted in the first two cells. The weakly coupled cell resulted in a trapped mode which was mostly concentrated in this cell and had a very high $Q_{ext} > 1000$. This parasitic mode introduced technical difficulties of tuning the operating mode frequency and added the risk of spurious monotron oscillations (see [39, 40] and 6.4.3 for more details). For these reasons, it was decided to proceed with the 2-cell design. The geometry parameters are presented in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Output cavity geometry parameters (z_0 is the longitudinal position regarding the center of the first cavity).

Below two methods are presented to optimize this design: the first one is based on a clustering algorithm using Klyc, while the second one is based on a gradient descent using MAGIC. The goal for these optimizations is to achieve the highest efficiency. The surface electric fields were constrained to be lower than 100 MV/m (1.1 of the Killpatrick limit) to avoid the RF breakdown.

6.2.2.1 Optimization based on Klyc and a clustering algorithm

Klyc simulation with single-layer disks may provide fast but less accurate results than multi-layer disk or PIC simulations. Therefore, such a simulation was used to test a large set of output cavity configurations. Nine parameters defining a configuration are optimized:

two RF parameters (the cavity frequency f_0 and the coupling factor Q_{ext}) and the geometric parameters presented in Figure 18, except the parameter $r_{tunnel\ in}$ which has been set to 4 mm during the bunching circuit optimization and $r_{tunnel\ out}$ which has been fixed at 5.5 mm to take the beam expansion into account.

The optimization is based on an iterative process. For each iteration, 200 configurations providing the highest efficiency are selected, the lowest efficiency among these configurations defining a threshold efficiency. The cavities for which the maximum electric field is higher than 100 MV/m are penalized. Based on their parameters, these configurations are gathered into clusters defining a new search area. Random configurations within this new area are generated and simulated using the batched jobs option from Klyc. The bunching circuit is the one presented in Table 3. If the specified frequency f_0 does not fit with the geometric parameters, the configuration is ignored and not simulated.

The convergence of the algorithm is depicted in Figure 19. The algorithm selects progressively the configurations for which the geometry fits with the specified frequency (at the end, almost all generated configurations are simulated) while the decreasing search area converges to local maxima (the threshold efficiency is the same for the last iterations).

Figure 19: Clustering algorithm progression.

For a reliable result, final batched jobs are performed among the configurations providing better than 72% efficiency, changing the number of disk layers from 1 to 4. The best configuration, simulated with four-layer disks, provides about 65% efficiency with a maximum surface electric field of about 90 MV/m.

6.2.2.2 Optimization based on PIC simulations

MAGIC 2D code [21] was used as the primary tool to estimate the output power of the optimized klystron. Relatively fast (for PIC) MAGIC simulations allowed for a fine

meshing with each klystron cavity containing at least 22 longitudinal mesh lines and at least 50 transverse mesh lines. The 2D simulations take advantage of the rotational symmetry of the klystron cavities, and ignore the asymmetry introduced by the waveguide couplers in the input and the output cavities. Instead, the input power coupler is modeled by an antenna, and the output coupler is modeled by a cylindrically symmetric absorbing region. The conductivity of the absorbing region is tuned to get the desired Q_{ext} of the output waveguide coupler.

First, the already designed bunching circuit (Table 3) was simulated separately and the beam was exported before the output cavity. This beam was then imported in much faster stand-alone output cavity simulations. Once the output cavity was optimized, full klystron simulations were performed to eliminate the error associated with beam exportation.

The gradient descent algorithm was used to tune the cavity geometry for maximum RF efficiency. For the 2-cell configuration, the tuned parameters included the positions and the lengths of both cells, the difference between the cells radii, the iris radius, the exit beam pipe radius, and the absorber conductivity to tune the loaded Q-factor of the cavity. For any vector in this parameter space, the frequency of the operating π -mode was tuned before the beam simulation. The frequency tuning was done by adjusting the radii of the cells. To prevent the mesh lines from shifting, the parameter space was discretized in accordance with the mesh steps in the longitudinal and radial directions (0.1 mm and 0.2 mm respectively). The iris thickness was constrained to be not lower than 1.5 mm for the manufacturing feasibility. The surface electric fields were constrained to be lower than 100 MV/m (1.1 of the Killpatrick limit) to avoid the RF breakdown. Care was taken to make sure that the cavity walls did not intercept any electrons. The resulting output cavity with the beam is shown in Figure 20 and its dimensions are listed in Table 4.

6.2.2.3 Discussion regarding both optimizations

The comparison of cavities obtained with both optimization processes is presented in Figure 21. The optimized parameters are gathered in Table 4. Despite both methods are different, they converge to very similar designs. The shapes are almost the same, the cavity positions differ by about 3.5 mm but the shape of the π -mode electric field is very similar: stronger in the first cell for better interaction with the beam, weaker in the second cell, where most of the bunch is already decelerated. The gap of the first cell is large enough to avoid a high electric field surface and to gather most of the energy cavity.

Figure 20: Output cavity model in MAGIC-2D with the beam shown in red. The absorbing region is shown in purple. Shims for fine frequency tuning are shown in blue. The center of the input cavity is at $z = 10.75$ mm in this simulation.

Parameter	Optimization in Klyc	Optimization in MAGIC 2D
r_1 (mm)	10.66	10.6
r_2 (mm)	11.50	11.2
$r_{tunnel\ in}$ (mm)	4.0	4.0
$r_{tunnel\ out}$ (mm)	5.5	5.0
r_{iris} (mm)	4.05	4.0
z_0 (mm)	278.92	282.35
gap_1 (mm)	4.08	3.1
gap_2 (mm)	2.63	2.7
l_{iris} (mm)	1.70	1.8
Q_{ext}	79.86	52.6
f_0 (GHz)	11.990	11.994

Table 4: Output cavity dimensions resulting from the Klyc and MAGIC 2D optimizations.

A MAGIC simulation of the cavity optimized in Klyc estimated its maximum electric field to be 98 MV/m with a 59.2% efficiency. Changing the Q_{ext} parameter from 79.86 to 56, it is possible to increase the efficiency to 62.4% with a maximum electric field of about 82 MV/m.

The cavity optimized with MAGIC, simulated with the same parameters in Klyc, validated the surface electric field lower than 100 MV/m. Klyc simulation also showed a slightly lower efficiency of 60.7% given the parameters from MAGIC, however, it could be increased up to 65.7% by changing the Q_{ext} parameter from 52.6 to 85. Then the highest electric field estimated in Klyc would be about 120 MV/m.

Figure 21: Comparison of the cavities optimized with MAGIC and with Klyc. Left: geometry of the output cavity. Right: Electric field on axis (eigenmode simulation for stored energy of 1 J)

The klystron performances presented in the next paragraphs are calculated using the cavity optimized with MAGIC.

6.3 Cavity geometries

6.3.1 Intermediate cavities

Two types of cavity geometries, presented in Figure 22, have been investigated and used in the simulations, depending on the solver. The first geometry "GEO1" consists of a simple pillbox cavity, tuned by changing its radius. This geometry was used in Klyc and MAGIC solvers. The second geometry "GEO2" consists again of a pillbox cavity but the radius is the same for all cavities and the frequency is tuned via small volumes on both sides of the cavity. The tuning is performed by changing the longitudinal geometry. This geometry was used to perform simulations on CST because the tuning of the cavities did not change the transverse mesh.

Figure 22: Intermediate cavity geometries: GEO1: used in Klyc and MAGIC with a radial tuning (left); GEO2: used in CST with a longitudinal tuning (right).

The tuned parameters calculated on CST are presented in Table 5.

Cavity ID	f (GHz)	gap (mm)	GEO1	GEO2		
			R_{cav} (mm)	R_{cav} (mm)	dz_{Tune} (mm)	dR_{Tune} (mm)
2	12.000	2.2	10.591	9.5	0.596	2.5
3	12.552	2.2	10.197	9.5	0.390	2.5
4	12.577	2.2	10.180	9.5	0.381	2.5
5	12.176	2.2	10.462	9.5	0.528	2.5
6	12.236	2.2	10.419	9.5	0.505	2.5
7	12.105	2.2	10.514	9.5	0.555	2.5

Table 5: Intermediate cavity dimensions.

6.3.2 First cavity

During the simulations with CST, the first cavity was coupled to the beam via an antenna. To manufacture this klystron it would be possible to couple this cavity using a waveguide, which dimensions would correspond to the reference WR75 rectangular waveguide. The geometry, presented in Figure 23, would be similar to GEO2, but with a larger gap, to facilitate the insertion of a slot between the cavity and the waveguide. The geometry parameters are presented in Table 6.

Figure 23: First cavity geometry

A (mm)	19.1
B (mm)	9.53
a_{Slot} (mm)	10
b_{Slot} (mm)	4
l_{Slot} (mm)	5.11
R_{drift} (mm)	4
R_{CAV} (mm)	9.5
dR_{Tune} (mm)	2.5
dz_{Tune} (mm)	0.379
gap (mm)	5
Q_{ext}	270
f_{loaded} (GHz)	11.988

Table 6: Input cavity dimensions.

6.3.3 Last cavity

The geometry for the double gap output cavity, coupled with a rectangular waveguide is presented in Figure 24. The insertion of a slot in the first cell may affect its frequency and the axial electric field. Therefore, the cell radii have been slightly modified regarding

the one of the double gap output cavity optimized on MAGIC 2D and presented in Table 4. The final dimensions for this cavity are presented in Table 7.

Figure 24: Last cavity geometry (for illustrative purposes, proportions in longitudinal and transverse directions may not be respected).

A (mm)	19.1
B (mm)	9.53
a_{Slot} (mm)	10
b_{Slot} (mm)	3.1
l_{Slot} (mm)	4
r_1 (mm)	10.06
r_2 (mm)	11.22
$r_{tunnel\ in}$ (mm)	4.0
$r_{tunnel\ out}$ (mm)	5.0
r_{iris} (mm)	4.0
gap_1 (mm)	3.1
gap_2 (mm)	2.7
l_{iris} (mm)	1.8
Q_{ext}	53.7
f_{loaded} (GHz)	11.995

Table 7: Input cavity dimensions.

The axial electric field for the geometry without waveguide, optimized with MAGIC 2D, and the one for the modified geometry with waveguide are depicted in Figure 25. Both

are in a good agreement, validating the tuning performed to correct the slot insertion.

Figure 25: Axial electric field in the last cavity with waveguide and without waveguide. Cavities are loaded with 1 J.

6.4 Klystron performance

6.4.1 Output power and efficiency

The final klystron configuration was simulated in MAGIC 2D for 600 ns with no instabilities observed - see Figure 26. Nevertheless, since a pulse length can be longer than 600 ns, a monotron instability check (see 6.4.3) was performed. To get the output RF power P_{out} , some post-processing was done to the absorbed power shown in Figure 26. First, an eigenmode simulation in Ansys HFSS [41] was performed to estimate the Ohmic losses in the walls of the output cavity, which were then subtracted from the absorbed power. Then, a Fourier analysis of the absorbed power was employed to filter out the small signals at the higher harmonics, leaving only the fundamental frequency of 11.994 GHz.

Figure 26: Power dissipated in the absorbing region of the output cavity, as recorded by the MAGIC simulation.

The output power dependence on the input power P_{in} is shown in Figure 27 (left), as simulated in MAGIC 2D. At $P_{in} = 580 \text{ W}$ the klystron is in the saturated regime and further increase in P_{in} does not result in increased efficiency, hence this value was chosen as the nominal input power. The final output power is 18.85 MW, corresponding to the RF efficiency of 65.5%. The 3dB bandwidth of the klystron is estimated to be 96 MHz, as is shown in Figure 27 (right).

Figure 27: Output power as a function of the input RF power supplied to the first cavity (left) and the input RF frequency (right), as simulated in MAGIC 2D.

The final klystron configuration was also simulated on CST as depicted in Figure 28 and on Klyc, using 4 layers-disk and $Q_{ext} = 85$. The CST simulation was the most difficult to implement and needed to control a lot of parameters. For instance, the performances of the cavities were highly dependant on the mesh generation, which had to be well controlled. To reduce the number of parameters that have to be controlled, the coupling on the first and last

cavity was not performed with waveguides as presented in Figure 23 and Figure 24 but with loop couplers. This technique also reduces the number of cells in mesh and so decreases significantly the simulation time.

The power balance of the klystron, obtained with these different solvers is displayed in Table 8. There is a very good agreement between MAGIC 2D and Klyc simulations. The lower efficiency obtained with CST could be explained by the double gap output cavity performances which are not fully controlled in CST. This could also explain that the deceleration of the bunched beam is not optimal and so the kinetic losses are higher. For all the simulation tools, the total power balance shows that each simulation is self-consistent within 0.4%. Regarding the Klyc and MAGIC 2D results, we can conclude that the RF efficiency of the klystron is about 65.5 %.

Figure 28: Simulation on CST: geometry (top), beam particle modulation along the tube (bottom).

	Klyc	MAGIC 2D	CST
P_{out} extracted RF power	65.73%	65.45%	61.20%
P lost to the kinetic energy of the spent beam	28.28%	28.29%	34.91%
Difference between the EM fields power of the spent and the initial beam	3.65%	4.87%	1.70%
P lost to the Ohmic dissipation in the walls	2.34%	1.85%	2.15%
Total power balance	100%	100.4%	99.96%

Table 8: Extracted and lost power expressed as fractions of the initial DC beam power $I_0 V_k$.

6.4.2 Surface fields

The output cavity is by far the most critical part of the klystron in terms of the surface fields. Hence, making sure the electric field at the surface is lower than the breakdown limit has been one of the priorities of the output cavity design. For a klystron operation at 12 GHz and a low duty factor (such as that required for Compact Light or CLIC), we considered the limit of 100 MV/m. This value corresponds to 1.1 times the Killpatrick limit and is a reasonable assumption based on the XBOX experience. Figure 29 shows the electric field obtained from the MAGIC 2D simulation of the designed klystron. The fields in the four key points and everywhere on the surface stays below the breakdown limit. The simulation performed in CST validates this result, with a 100.07 MV/m maximum electric field estimated in the last cavity.

Figure 29: Electric field in the output cavity as a result of a PIC simulation in MAGIC 2D. Left: shape of the excited field lines. Right: magnitudes of the field at the selected points as a function of time.

6.4.3 Klystron stability

The kladistron design from the earlier studies done in the framework of EuCARD-2 has presumably suffered from the reflected electrons instability (see section 5). After having learned this lesson, we made sure that the present 12 GHz klystron design for ARIES would not be prone to it thanks to the much lower small signal gain. If a collector design is added to this study, it would be desirable to repeat the rigorous analysis of the reflected electrons instability. Below we analyze another type of instability – spurious monotron oscillations.

Monotron oscillations can often occur in klystrons with multi-cell output cavities. This instability is a result of the interaction of the unbunched beam with the parasitic modes in the cavity. Under certain conditions, the energy can start flowing from the beam to the mode, resulting in excessively high fields and potentially fatal beam oscillations. The necessary

condition for the monotron oscillations to occur is [40]

$$G_b + G_l \leq 0 \quad (10)$$

where G_b is the beam conductance and $G_l = 1/((R/Q)Q_L)$ is the equivalent circuit conductance of the cavity mode. We followed the procedure described in [29] to estimate G_b , and performed HFSS eigenmode simulations to estimate G_l for the modes 0 and π of the output cavity. The resulting beam-loaded conductance is shown in Figure 30 as a function of the cathode voltage. As we can see, the monotron instability cannot occur at any point during the voltage ramp-up, including the nominal voltage of 240 kV.

Figure 30: Beam-loaded conductance (normalized over $G_0 = I_0/V_0$) as a function of the cathode voltage.

6.4.4 Scan of the output power

Once the RF klystron design is fully completed, it can be interesting to see how its performance varies with respect to the output power. For this, we do no additional tuning and do not change the input power, only varying the DC beam power. The beam current and the cathode voltage are varied in a way that preserves the beam perveance (Eq. 1). The resulting efficiency is plotted in Figure 31, as calculated by MAGIC 2D and KlyC solvers. The results show that in the range of the output power from 16 MW to 26 MW the RF efficiency remains higher than 60%. It is also interesting to note that the efficiency slightly increases when the output power goes beyond the optimized point ($P_{out} = 18.85 MW$). However, this efficiency increase happens at the expense of the surface fields that rise above the defined threshold (up to 113 MV/m in MAGIC and 137 MV/m in KlyC for the highest

power point). Nevertheless, if the increased surface fields and the cathode voltage can be tolerated, it is more efficient to run the klystron at the output power of around 23.5 MW (MAGIC) or 20 MW (KlyC).

Figure 31: Efficiency as a function of the output RF power, assuming constant beam perveance.

7 Conclusion and perspectives

Within the frame of the ARIES WP4, CEA, helped partly by advice from CERN, ESS, and PSI, performed a design study of a 12 GHz klystron with about 20 MW peak power, intending to improve its efficiency by more than 10% compared to the efficiency of the commercially existing klystrons, which is at most 50%. CEA had already initiated a design study of a 12 GHz klystron for CLIC in the frame of EuCARD-2, and had built a prototype at 5 GHz based on a retrofit of an existing Thales TH2166 klystron. The present study builds upon the lessons learned from it. The peak power has been chosen to be between 8 MW and 50 MW, for which CERN already had designs underway with SLAC, and was also a niche that could be of use for the future CompactLight FEL project.

This study focuses mainly on the design of the interaction line and the multi-cell output cavity, and the RF efficiency obtained with different simulation techniques is about 65%, achieving thus the initial goal for improving efficiency by more than 10 percent. The key parameters of this design are summarized in Table 9.

As far as beam focusing is concerned, we discussed use of alternatives solutions less power hungry than a normal conducting solenoid, as the power dissipated in a normal conducting focusing magnet tends to be a big contribution to the overall power consumption for low duty cycle operation. Gun and collector remain to be designed to fully complete this study.

Frequency	11.994 GHz
Perveance	$1.02 \times 10^{-6} A/V^{3/2}$
Cathode voltage	240 kV
Beam current	120 A
Focusing B-field	0.39 T
Output RF power	18.85 MW
RF efficiency	65.5%
3 dB bandwidth	96 MHz
Surface E-field	$< 100 \text{ MV/m}$
Klystron interaction length (between gun and collector)	300 mm

Table 9: Key parameters of the designed klystron.

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